

Associazione International University College of Turin

“The CIE Research Project of the Human Rights and Migration Law Clinic in Turin”

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Executive Summary

The International University College of Turin (IUC) in cooperation with the Faculties of Law of the University of Turin and the Eastern Piedmont University in Alessandria and in partnership with the *Associazione Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione* (ASGI) is conducting a study on the detention conditions of migrants in the Centre for Identification and Expulsion (CIE) of Turin. The CIE Research Project is part of a clinical legal training program (Human Rights and Migration Law Clinic) and is currently involving six graduate and undergraduate students of the IUC, the University of Turin and the Eastern Piedmont University under the supervision of IUC faculty staff and ASGI lawyers.

The research began in January 2012 and is limited to experiences of detention that occurred between January 2011 and April 2012. The objective is to investigate and analyse whether the treatment of immigration detainees in Turin's CIE meets Italian, European and international human rights standards. The project also aims to inquire into systemic and individual problems faced by detainees, their families and people who work in CIE or have contact with CIE in a professional or voluntary capacity. The study consists in a qualitative survey (mainly interviews) aimed at collecting and presenting holistic information about experiences of immigration detention in Turin. Therefore interviews are targeted at a broad cross-section of subjects, such as: current and former detainees, their family members, lawyers, journalists, religious personnel, CIE staff, medical personnel, government officials, judges and so on.

The information gathering stage of the CIE Research Project has only recently begun, therefore conclusions cannot be drawn yet. Nevertheless, a number of relevant issues have already emerged from the first interviews both to CIE detainees and to professionals and volunteers who have contact with CIE. This introductory paper aims to highlight some of these issues, including but not limited to: the problem of understanding what CIE is; the effects of detention on family relationships and on detainees' physical and mental health; CIE detention as a further deprivation of freedom for former convicts; the controversial role of embassies and consulates in the identification procedure; the lack of activities and the daily hurdles suffered by migrants inside CIE.

Although this study is only at its first stages, as we scratch the surface of the above mentioned issues, it becomes increasingly apparent that a thorough investigation into Turin's CIE environment will produce important outcomes. We are convinced that we cannot discuss about alternatives to CIE as long as knowledge on CIEs and immigration detention are so limited. The first aim of our project is actually to increase public awareness of the major problems related to CIE detention.

I. Introduction to the Human Rights and Migration Law Clinic in Turin & Research Project into Turin's Centre for Identification and Expulsion (CIE)

The enforcement of human rights especially in the area of migration is an important and ongoing challenge for all parts of society at global, regional, national and local levels. Well-trained and responsible lawyers and other professionals can play an important role within this process.

The recently started Human Rights & Migration Law Clinic (HRMLC) in Turin (commenced in October 2011) wishes to establish a new style of legal education in the Piedmont region by encouraging students through experiential learning – learning by doing – for academic credit to emphasise the sensitisation of students as future professionals to the problems of social justice and to foster a sense of social responsibility.

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Furthermore, the HRMLC Program strives to offer research and legal assistance to under-represented individuals within Turin, complementing the already existing support provided by local organisations working locally for the benefit of migrants.

The HRMLC is a joint program initiated and coordinated by the International University College of Turin² in cooperation with the Faculties of Law of the University of Turin and the Eastern Piedmont University in Alessandria and in partnership with the *Associazione Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione* (ASGI)³.

As part of their practical clinical experience, six clinical students are involved in a practical legal analysis related to the legal framework and the praxis insight of the Centre for Identification and Expulsion (CIE) in Turin.

The research has been motivated by the fact that according to a number of associations, institutions and organisations at local, national, European and international level the current praxis of administrative detention of irregular migrants in CIEs raises a number of concerns in Italy (and elsewhere in Europe). In particular, it is often claimed that the inconsistency between the explicit and implicit aims of CIEs seems to produce in general terms a source for abuses, inefficiency, disease and violations of human rights. This became true especially in 2011 and is of particular relevance to Turin.

In real terms, the clinical activities consist of studying the legal framework (EU level, national level) of CIEs, screening the presence of detained migrants in the period January 2011-April 2012, verifying the judicial protection of detained migrants and analysing the detention conditions. The necessary information is gathered by data and literature analysis and through interviews/visits.

From a methodological point of view, the clinical students organise themselves as a group and, under the supervision and with the support of the clinical staff (Prof. Ulrich Stege and Avv. Maurizio Veglio), manage the different activities, researches, interviews etc. on their own.

For what concerns specifically the gathering of first-hand information, a qualitative survey composed both of interviews and questionnaires is taking place at the present moment. This stage of the research project aims at investigating issues related to migration law and human rights law in CIE as well as broader socio-legal issues including mental health, the effects of separation from family, experiences of language and cultural barriers and any hurdles faced to accessing legal assistance or in understanding the Italian legal framework.

The sample population is constituted by different categories of interviewees. Therefore, three different questionnaire forms were prepared, but each form is divided in the same sections, so that answers given by different subjects on the same issue are easily comparable.

- The first group of interviewees consists in current and former detainees (with current detainees we are using telephone interviews).
- The second questionnaire form is targeted to lawyers, religious personnel and NGOs staff who enter/entered inside CIE. A similar albeit modified version of this form is used for detainees' family members as well as for journalists and researchers working on the issue of CIE.
- The third group of interviewees is made up of the CIE personnel: CIE director, Red Cross staff, guards, medical staff (doctors, nurses, psychologists) and social workers. We may also be able to interview judges and local authorities' representatives.

II. Issues Surfacing from our Preliminary Interviews

We only recently began the data collection stage of this study, having interviewed ten people; five were CIE detainees, and five were people who have contact with CIE in a professional or voluntary capacity

² See for more detail: www.iuctorino.it.

³ See for more detail on the HRMLC in Turin: "*The HUMAN RIGHTS & MIGRATION LAW CLINIC in Turin, a joint program between the Faculties of Law of the Universities of Turin and Eastern Piedmont in Alessandria and the International University College of Turin*", Paper presented by Ulrich Stege for the Conference on "Clinical Legal Education in Europe", Brescia 3rd February 2012.

(lawyers, religious personnel and a journalist). This introductory paper aims to highlight some of the issues that are coming out of these first interviews. Given the small number of interviews conducted, we are not in a position to draw any conclusions yet. Moreover, in order to draw holistic and considered conclusions, we are also requesting official information and statistics from governmental and non-governmental organisations involved in CIE (in particular from Red Cross-CIE administration, local Questura, and the head of the judiciary in charge of detention validation and extension). With time, we hope to be able to develop a more holistic picture of the following issues.

1. Family Relationships and CIE

With large distances between family and CIE, for the detainees already interviewed telephone calls seem to be the principal way of staying connected to loved ones. For instance, we interviewed one lady whose nine year-old daughter in Rome had not been able to visit her due to the distance between Rome and Turin. The daughter was born in Italy, attends school here and resides with the grandmother who has a valid visa to live in Italy, *“The problem is that I am stressed because I cannot see my daughter [...] I want to die, because I miss my family too much”*, reported the interviewee. We have been told of another lady who was separated from her four children and taken from Reggio Calabria to Turin, *“...she had 4 children living in Reggio Calabria and she wrote a letter saying that it is inhuman to separate a mother from her children. I still have the letter. So basically parents are separated from their children and nowadays this happens very often because inside CIE you find people who have been living in Italy for a long time, with a family here and children who were born here”*.

So far, detainees have mentioned that they cannot afford to buy telephone credit to stay in touch with loved ones. Information is consistently coming out of the interviews with detainees to suggest that detainees are given 3 x 5 euro international telephone cards (worth a total value of 15 euros for their stay in CIE). We have consistently been told that they receive this 15 euros of credit in their first weeks in Turin’s CIE, but allegedly they are not given any free telephone credit after this 15 euros of credit has been spent.

Connection with family is not limited to telephone calls, and those with loved ones who can afford to visit Turin appear to have the option to receive visitors. However, one interviewee alleged the following limitations with the visiting system:

“The visiting hours are every afternoon from 2 to 6 o’clock and there is only one room for visits. The problem is that there is only one “channel” for all kinds of visits: for diplomatic personnel, for lawyers, for family members. So if there is a consul or a lawyer talking with a detainee, family members have to wait for their turn, even though they already have the authorization and they may have done a long journey to come to Turin. Sometimes time is not enough and they have to go away and come back the following day with their bags as well. But there are at least two more rooms which are empty and not used and that could be used for visits. Once we complained about this and they opened an extra room. But a common answer to our requests is that there is not enough personnel to open a second room for visits. Once a Tunisian detainee went crazy when his wife, who had come from France and was pregnant, was waiting outside CIE because in that moment there was a consul; she was waiting on the street and she felt faint. They let her enter and sit on a bench in the courtyard and at the end the Red Cross took her to the hospital”.

One young man in his 20s expressed his stress because he felt that he could not tell his mother in his country of origin about his detention in CIE. This young man was scared that his mother would not understand the meaning of CIE, which he said did not exist as a concept in his country of origin. He feared that his mother might assume that if he was in detention it was a criminal jail. Prior to being detained in CIE, he was working and regularly sending money to his home country to support his family. He spoke with sadness about how he felt forced into a position where he needed to lie to his family, telling them that he was not working much in Italy and this is why he stopped being able to send home money. In reality, he stopped sending home money because he has been detained in CIE.

2. Understanding what CIE is

Understanding the concept of “CIE” is not only difficult for family members who live far away from Italy’s shores. A professional associated with CIE explained their perception of the issue:

“For those who were in jail and are detained in CIE waiting for repatriation, the reason is quite clear. For those who are in CIE because of the crime of illegal immigration, it is more difficult to understand. They don’t understand that “illegal immigration” can be a crime, also because many of them entered with a visa. For example these Nigerian women, after 60 days their visa expires, they do not know they have to apply for documents and if they are caught on the street they are immediately brought to CIE. But they do not understand the crime of illegal immigration, they would understand better the “moral” crime of prostitution. So they always ask us the reason why they are still inside the CIE”.

3. Prison and CIE

So far, we have only interviewed four detainees who were moved from jail to CIE at the end of their prison sentences. However, each of the four CIE detainees adamantly responded that jail was better than CIE. The perspective that CIE has worse conditions than prison has been supported by different professionals associated with CIE. For example, three different professional interviewees described the comparison as follows:

“They [CIE administration] say the center is not a jail, I say not only that it is a jail, but that it is much worse than a jail. In jail rights are respected and detainees are treated as human beings, while inside CIE there are no clear rules, staff and guards could do whatever they want because there is nobody to control them”.

“They [detained migrants who were in prison before entering CIE] say that in jail they lived better than inside CIE. In jail there were activities and they could work and gain some money for themselves and for their families”.

“A relevant problem is the lack of activities, above all for those who come from jail. It’s more difficult for them to make time goes by, because in jail there were activities, in CIE there is none”.

Ex-prisoners noted the lack of activities in CIE in comparison to jail: *“I did “scuola media” [middle school] in jail”, or, “It was better, in jail there was a gym, there are games”.* Moreover, the space and facilities in CIE have been compared to jail: *“Where I was [in jail] I had a room for two people, we also had a little stove to be able to cook”.* Another difficulty highlighted was the psychological impact of not knowing when you are leaving CIE, in comparison to the more exact dates given to criminal prisoners who would like to know when their sentence will finish.

We are not yet in a position to draw conclusions, however as we conduct more interviews with both detainees and other parties we hope to discover more information on the striking outcome of this comparison.

4. Isolation

Isolation and boredom in CIE have been raised in interviews with detainees as well as professionals/volunteers: *“Detainees inside CIE do nothing, they only eat and sleep. There are only few activities (sport activities like football matches) depending on CIE staff willingness. Detainees’ days are empty; the staff brings them lunch at a certain time, dinner at a certain time, then they can watch TV, but very often TV is broken”.*

Detainees living in different areas of Turin’s CIE have mentioned the same names of dedicated religious personnel and volunteers who enter CIE and provide some relief from boredom; a new person to talk to and connection to the outside world.

5. Some Day-to-Day Issues Faced when Living in CIE

Both detainees and professionals/volunteers who have visited CIE have commented on the price of food, drinks and other items (i.e. soap, shampoo) that are available for sale inside CIE. Allegations have been made that these products cost double the price of what they would cost outside CIE.

Detainees have expressed humiliation and frustration at the difficulty of trying to shave their beards: *“The blades to do a beard, with three machines to do the whole centre’s beards. It is a shame!”.* A professional

also highlighted this issue: *“...and this was one of the greatest problems, because there were people who had to wait up to one month to be shaved and they were suffering about this being “untidy”. There were people who had a barbershop in Tunisia: they said they could have shaved everybody and were frustrated about waiting for someone else to come and shave them”.*

The ability to shave one’s beard appears to be about more than hygiene or routine; it is a question of controlling the small parts of one’s day. The lack of autonomy over the little things such as shaving inside CIE is being described repeatedly. Perhaps it is the little things that make a daily difference to a far larger anguish: freedom. A strong sentiment of absolute dependency has come through the detainee interviews, and this seems to be supported by professionals interviewed thus far:

“The worst feeling is that of being totally dependent on somebody else for everything, even to light a cigarette. The feeling of being always waiting for some-body else to do something for you. They say they do not ask for charity, they ask for freedom”.

“The greatest issue is freedom, I think that any other problem is a matter of secondary importance. People do not understand the reason why they have to throw away one year and a half of their own life inside a cage”.

6. The Time Taken for Consular Visits and the Identification of Third Country Nationals

We hope to collect more substantive data about the time that the third-country consulates take to identify CIE detainees who claim to come from that third-country. All the professionals and volunteers interviewed so far noted that some countries seem to be substantially faster than others when it comes to assisting CIE detainees who claim to be citizens of that third-country:

“Some consulates do not send anyone to identify their citizens, neither in jail nor inside CIE. They do not send any officials, documents, certificates or fingerprints. For example the Egyptian consulate: I don’t know nowadays, but in the past they never went in jail or CIE to identify migrants who reported to be Egyptian nationals. [...] And I really do not understand the reason why their own country of origin do not help them to get out of it, to get out of CIE. Detainees themselves suffer very much for this reason because they usually have very good relationships with their consulates and do not understand why those who are supposed to help and protect them do not do it”.

Another professional noted more generally about the CIEs in Italy;

“Your repatriation does not depend on you, but on your embassy/consulate: it depends on the fact that it recognises you as its own citizen. [...] But this is not easy, because some people are not registered at all, for example those who come from the countryside. There are migrants who have already been inside CIE three or four times and who have always been released because their embassy is not able to identify them. [...] There are also particular cases. For example in Modena’s CIE I was told: “we do not host Chinese people because their embassy does not cooperate: if it does not help us identify them, we cannot repatriate them”.

7. Medical Attention

So far we have received very mixed reports in relation to medical care in CIE, and we are not yet in a position to draw conclusions. However, the following and worrying allegation has been made:

“Before a detainee is taken to the infirmary it takes a long time. This happened with two episodes of epileptic shocks: the staff was called again and again and it took half an hour/an hour for someone to come. They kept telling us that they had already been informed about that. In such cases the pill you need to take is always the same and they did not give it to him. Once a guy had swallowed something, he was lying close to the gate, he remained there for hours and nobody arrived. It takes so much time because doctors cannot enter the areas, it’s the Red Cross staff who has to take detainees to the infirmary”.

Moreover, allegations have been made about a supposed over-use of psychotropic drugs such as Rivotril and Valium. We have highlighted this subject as an issue for further investigation.

On the other hand, very positive comments have also been made in relation to medical care in CIE. One detainee was happy with the way that an illness she had when she came into CIE was proactively treated by medical staff in CIE.

Finally, the issue of self-harm and self-mutilation has been raised:

“They [detainees] often swallow screws (of the refectory’s tables and benches). They swallow all sort of things, like the cleaner, batteries, and so on in order to go to the hospital. Because it often happens that when they go to the hospital then they are released, they are not taken back to CIE. Many of them try to slash their wrists and some of them succeed in doing it and there is blood everywhere. Sometimes they jump off the roofs to break their legs. Sometimes they just climb on the roofs or they go on hunger strike to attract attention on their case. Another case is that of the Egyptian guy in seclusion who tried to hang himself: he was taken to the hospital and then he was released”.

III. Conducting a Reliable and Ethical Research Project

The interviews with detainees have been particularly confronting on a professional and emotional level. We have spoken to detainees who mentioned serious health issues as a response to CIE, including previous suicide attempts and hunger strikes. As a group, we have worked together with our supervising professor and lawyer to discuss the ethical issues raised by interviewing detainees and former detainees who are in extremely vulnerable positions. We are endeavouring to conduct interviews with sensitivity, to maintain neutrality, respect anonymity and not to unrealistically raise expectations about the project. All interviewees are always informed about our research methodology and purposes and are required to express their consent before taking part in it. Detainees so far have been very enthusiastic about participating in the study, and about putting us in contact with other detainees in their areas. Being an international research group, we are also trying our best to overcome language barriers so that detainees who do not speak Italian will not be excluded from the research. As a team we have worked through these ethical issues, and we hope to be able to produce a profound, neutral and reliable study that has been conducted in a sensitive and ethical manner.

IV. Conclusion

We are in the early stages of data collection and unable to draw any substantive conclusions yet. However, as we scratch the surface of the above mentioned issues, it becomes increasingly apparent that a thorough investigation of Turin’s CIE will produce important results. We will endeavour to continue interviewing and collecting data on Turin’s CIE.

We are six student researchers from five different countries. In August, some of us will return to our home countries, and others will continue working in the field of human rights, immigration and detention of migrants in Italy. However, we all hope that through this research project we can produce a first in-depth academic study of Turin’s CIE, whilst simultaneously learning about international, European and Italian human rights standards that will help us to continue our own research, policy or legal work in our home countries in the future.

CIEs exist as a controversial element of migration law in many countries, and they are an environment that must be researched. We hope that this small study can help to contribute providing more access information about Turin’s CIE for policy makers, civil society, academics and the public to consider. In order to produce a holistic study, we are striving to find information from diverse perspectives, including current and former detainees and their families who have first-hand experiences of CIE or how CIE has affected their lives and relationships.

Most importantly, we would like to thank every-one who has generously volunteered their time and expertise to participate in our research project on human rights in Turin’s CIE.